

Precision agriculture for New Zealand potatoes – effect of variable yield, tuber size and income

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Abstract

This paper integrated geospatial soil and potato crop harvest characteristics to analyse geospatial crop profitability, and to aid crop management decision-making processes in future years.

Background

For the majority of arable grain and forage crops, yield is the key driver of income, providing the crop meets a minimum quality standard; the income per tonne of product is fixed. Potatoes, however, can give a different return per tonne depending on the size range of the tubers harvested, with values varying from \$1,000/tonne or more for specialist, gourmet potatoes; to \$200-300/tonne for processing potatoes; to no value for potatoes outside of the marketable tuber size range. For example, one New Zealand processor requires supplied tubers to be within a size range of 45-80 mm. Tubers outside the marketable size range still incur costs of production, harvesting and handling, without returning any value. Therefore, it is important to understand what is driving this tuber size variation as well as yield variation, and how to alter the performance of the crop.

Methods

This work included two trial sites, one each in Canterbury and the Waikato. Details of the sites are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Site locations and properties

	Gray	McCarville
Location	Winchester, Canterbury	East Matamata, Waikato
Coordinates	-44.187366° 171.285423°	-37.804394° 175.783176°
Metres above sea level	40	61
Soil Type	Barrhill silty loam	Ngakura loam Eureka loam
Area (ha)	18	11.2
Irrigation	13 ha centre pivot 5 ha surface pipe	nil

The crops were grown according to farmer best practice. Irrigation at the Gray site was applied using a centre pivot irrigator to ensure the soil moisture content did not drop below 50% of the soils plant available water in the top 60 cm over 13 hectares, and by surface pipes moved by hand supplying Roto-rainer sprinklers over the remaining 5 hectares. No irrigation was applied to the McCarville site, and it received adequate rainfall across the growing season.

Hand Sampling

Prior to machine harvest, hand harvests were undertaken at multiple sites across the paddock and measured from the hand-harvested zone to identify variations in tuber size across the site. GPS locations were identified at approximately 50m apart. At each location, a typical row, not adjacent to any tramlines, had 1.5 metres marked from the middle of the gap between two plants along the row. From this 1.5 m plot, the number of stems was counted, and all tubers were carefully hand dug and placed in a sack. The maximum diameter of each individual tuber was then measured using potato sizing squares and recorded. Any tubers that fit through a 20mm square were discarded, and the total remaining tubers were weighed. Soil samples were collected from the top of the undisturbed bed immediately beside the end of the 1.5 m space was collected and placed in a bag with labelled with location number.

Soil samples were sent to a registered soil laboratory to be analysed for pH, Olsen P, K, Ca, Mg, Na, CEC, total base Saturation, potentially available nitrogen and anaerobically mineralisable nitrogen.

Machine harvest

Greentronics© yield monitoring systems were fitted to two Grimme GT 170 potato harvesters. These yield monitors measure yield and GPS coordinates every second, resulting in approximately 3,000 yield data points per hectare. After paddock harvest is completed, "back calibration" of the yield data is desirable to ensure that the yields measured by the harvester yield monitor were correct. For the Gray paddock, this yield was then "back-calibrated" against the known weighbridge results measured for the harvested crop. According to the harvester yield monitor, 1007 tonnes were harvested from the 18-hectare paddock. However, the weighbridge weighed total yield from the paddock was 868 tonnes. Therefore, 13.8% of the yield measured by the yield monitor was subtracted prior to analysis. Of the total 868 tonnes, 66.5 tonnes were rejected by the purchaser, due to being undersize or other issues. Therefore 8.3% was deducted from yields to account for rejects. This results in an equation to determine marketable yield of:

$$\text{Marketable yield (t/ha)} = \text{Monitor yield (t/ha)} \times 0.79$$

Back calibration was not undertaken for the McCarville site, but calibration was undertaken before harvest by weighing bins of potatoes that had been harvested through the yield monitor, and the yield monitor was adjusted.

Data Analysis

Yield & Gross Margin Maps

Within the data for each site some negative yield values were recorded, and were edited from the file along with impossibly high values. The data was successfully geo-rectified and it was possible to produce a range of yield maps. Gross margin was calculated using the value of the potatoes at \$254/tonne, and the following table of costs. No cost has been attributed for the value of the land, crop management or interest on input costs.

$$\text{Gross margin (\$/ha)} = (\text{Yield (t/ha)} \times \text{Potato value (\$/tonne)}) - \text{Costs (\$/ha)}$$

Table 2. Costs associated with growing potatoes

Operation	Cost (\\$/ha)
Cultivation	\$1100
Seed & planting	\$2160
Fertiliser	\$2860
Pesticides and application	\$1630
Harvesting	\$2290
Transport	\$840
TOTAL COST	\$8,590

Correlation analysis

The relationships amongst the soil parameters and tuber size data were analysed by Pearson's correlation coefficients. Principal components analysis (PCA) was subsequently used. PCA is a statistical method that identifies the variables in a multi-variate data set that allow the data to be best differentiated. PCA is preferred for analysing data with lots of variables as a way to reduce data dimensions. In this work, the information contained by all 13 variables used in the study can be sufficiently explained by 4-5 principal components.

Tuber size mapping using inverse distance weighted interpolation (IDW)

Ordinary kriging (OK) was used initially to interpolate the tuber size data. However, the kriging variograms for the McCarville (35 points) showed no spatial autocorrelation, which suggested that there were too few sampling points for the size of the field, and there were not enough data to compute Matheron's (1965) method of moments variogram reliably (Kerry et al., 2010). Therefore, inverse distance weighted interpolation (IDW) was used for mapping the McCarville site. Similar to OK, the value of a targeted variable at a new location can be derived as a weighted average from the inverse distances from all known points to the new point. IDW is available in many farm GIS software (e.g. AgLeader SMS™) and typically used in mapping soil samples where there are few, sparse data points.

Spatial clustering for site specific management

The main reason for soil sampling as a part of the investigation is to use it to assist in understanding the variation seen in the productivity maps. Figure 2 shows the harvest yield map for Gray site. The yield map was clustered using k-means with the map of 45-80mm tubers (Figure 5), which can be performed in 'FuzME', freeware developed by the Australian Centre for Precision Agriculture. The procedure for using the freeware has been described in detail by Taylor et al. (2007). These clusters can then be used to create management zones (MZ).

Results

Hand harvest

Hand harvest results showed a large range of tuber size throughout the paddocks. Tuber size results from the Gray site are given in Figure 1 below showing the variation in tuber size.

Figure 1. Potato tuber size variation from hand harvests at different locations in Gray potato paddock. Average tuber size is shown as the green square

In Figure 1 above the bottom of the column at each site indicates the smallest marketable tuber diameter size at that sample location, with the top of the bar indicating the largest tuber diameter. The green square indicates the average tuber diameter at that sample location. Large variations can be seen within the different bands, and similar trends can be seen in the McCarville site (data not presented).

Machine harvest

Data recorded by the yield monitor was cleaned and analysed and Figure 2 shows a geospatial map of potato yield at the Gray site, as mapped using AgLeader Technology SMS Advanced v17.20.

Figure 2. Spatial yield variation from potato harvest at Gray site

While yield is obviously important to the grower, the profitability of the crop is more important. From the yield data, spatial Gross Margin maps were generated for the trial sites using values for income and expenses in Table 1.

It can be seen that some areas of the Gray paddock are generating greater than \$5,000/ha profits, while some areas are not achieving breakeven. The average GM (excluding land, management and interest costs) was \$2,390/ha. Similar trends were seen at the McCarville site (data not presented).

Correlation analysis

Table 3 below gives a summary of the yield, average tuber size and soil characteristics of the three trial sites.

Table 3. Soil and crop characteristics from trial sites

	Gray	McCarville
Machine harvested yield (t/ha)	55.2	47.3
Proportion of 45–80 mm tuber (%)	77.6	63.7
pH	5.5	6.3
Olsen Phosphorus (mg/l)	48.6	45.7
Potentially Available Nitrogen (15cm deep, kg/ha)	86.2	68.4
Anaerobically Mineralisable N (µg/g)	53.6	62.9
Potassium (me/100g)	0.4	0.6
Calcium (me/100g)	7.7	8.2
Magnesium (me/100g)	0.9	1.7
CEC (me/100g)	14.7	3.2
Total Base Saturation (%)	61.5	52.7
Volume Weight (g/mL)	1.1	0.7

* Yield calculated from hand harvests

Principal Components Analysis (PCA) of the soil, tuber size and stem count data found that for the Gray site, 50.8% of the total variation was explained by the first two dimensions of the PCA (Figure 3). Sample locations with a higher proportion of the 45-80mm tubers tended to have a higher soil bulk density, but lower total base saturation, pH, calcium and magnesium. For the McCarville site, 55.6% of the total information was explained by the first two dimensions of the PCA (Figure 4). Sample locations with a higher proportion of the 45-80mm tubers also tended to have a higher Olsen Phosphorus, potassium and soil bulk density, but lower sodium concentration and stem counts.

Figure 3. PCA Correlation Matrix (left) and biplot (right) for Graysite

Figure 4. PCA Correlation Matrix (left) and Biplot (right) for McCarville site

Management zones

The 'FuzME' software can establish sets of clusters, or Management Zones (MZ), as shown in Figure 5 & Figure 6 below. The specific yield, size and soil characteristics for these clusters are shown in Table 4 and Table 5 below.

Table 4. Average yields, 45-80mm size tubers and soil properties within the clusters (McCarville site)

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Significance
Areas (ha)	6.54	4.73	
Yield (t/ha)	46.97	46.81	
Gross Margin (\$/ha)	\$3,340	\$3,300	
45-80 mm tubers	0.58	0.71	**
Stem counts	22.75	17.47	**
pH	6.26	6.29	ns
Olsen P (mg/l)	43.75	48.27	ns
Available N (15cm) (kg/ha)	68.70	67.93	ns
Anaerobically Mineralisable N (µg/g)	63.30	62.40	ns
Potassium (me/100g)	0.60	0.69	ns
Calcium (me/100g)	7.81	8.65	ns
Magnesium (me/100g)	1.65	1.73	ns
Sodium (me/100g)	2.15	2.00	ns
CEC (me/100g)	19.25	20.67	*
Total Base Saturation (%)	51.85	53.80	ns
Volume Weight (g/mL)	0.72	0.73	ns

Significance level 0.001 to 0.01**

0.01 to 0.05*

Table 5. Average yields, 45-80mm size tubers and soil properties within the clusters (Gray site)

	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Significance
Areas (ha)	3.9	3.7	4.2	6.3	
Yield (t/ha)	35.6	44.6	45.8	47.4	
Gross Margin (\$/ha)	\$452	\$2,738	\$3,043	\$3,450	
45-80 mm tubers	0.77	0.88	0.79	0.69	***
Stem counts	20.8	18.7	22.1	20.8	ns
pH	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.6	*
Olsen P (mg/l)	47.2	46.3	52	48.8	ns
Available N (15cm) (kg/ha)	82	79.3	95.1	88.2	**
Anaerobically Mineralisable N (µg/g)	50.4	49.2	58.3	55.6	**
Potassium (me/100g)	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	ns
Calcium (me/100g)	7.2	7.4	8.1	8.1	*
Magnesium (me/100g)	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	ns
Sodium (me/100g)	4.3	4.6	4.8	3.9	ns
CEC (me/100g)	14.4	14.2	15	15.1	ns
Total Base Saturation (%)	59.4	61.4	61.8	62.8	ns
Volume Weight (g/mL)	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	ns

Significance level 0.001 to 0.01**

0.01 to 0.05*

Discussion

Use of yield monitors

This work showed that the Greentronics yield monitoring units are sufficiently sensitive to measure field scale variations in potato yield, and the data appeared real and meaningful. Commercial harvesting of potato crops often involves the lifting of potatoes from one or more rows and placing them on top of adjacent rows, without the potatoes travelling over the weighing harvester belt, therefore the yield monitor records “0” yield. These potatoes are then harvested with the adjacent one or more rows, leading to the yield monitor recording the yield of two harvester passes as one. The operator must change setting on the yield monitor when this occurs to record the correct number of rows harvested. The user interface of the Greentronics unit is text based and not user friendly or intuitive, meaning recording these parameters is difficult. Efficient calibration procedures need to be identified and tested to accurately calibrate harvester-measured yield to actual yield, as weighed on a certified weighbridge.

Practical implications – Gray

The spatial potato yield data used to generate Figure 2 was delineated using k-mean clustering to generate the clusters, which are potential management zones (MZ) shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Potential management zones based on the potato yields and tuber size distribution

Yield – Gray

Cluster 1 yielded approximately 10 t/ha less than the other zones, and had significant differences in certain soil parameters when compared with the other zones. On discussion with the grower it was identified that the bulk of Zone 1 was irrigated by surface pipes, rather than automated centre pivot system, and the grower declared that they did not operate the surface pipe irrigation regularly enough to provide the same rate of irrigation to the crop as the centre-pivot irrigation. It is possible that the difference in soil parameters in MZ 1 could be because of the long-term effect of the different irrigation regime. Clusters 2, 3 & 4 had higher yields than cluster 1, as well as having higher pH, Ca and total base saturation (Table 5). However, only pH and Ca were significantly different between the clusters. Despite producing the highest total yield, Cluster 4 had the lowest proportion of tubers in the 45-80mm size range.

Grower planning – Gray

At the Gray site management induced variability can clearly be attributed to the effect of irrigation. Given the significant difference in soil pH and calcium levels between the MZ, the use of variable rate lime application could increase soil pH and calcium levels in MZ 1 and MZ 2 to provide better soil characteristics for crop production. An additional benefit would be the minimising the unnecessary spreading of lime on MZ 3 and MZ 4, which have higher soil pH and calcium levels. The grower might consider that when they grow potatoes in that paddock again they would rather grow a crop that is less dependent on irrigation.

Practical Implications – McCarville

The McCarville site is a long, skinny site, which is part of a larger block. Cluster analysis has identified that this site can be divided into two clusters, as shown in Table 5 above and Figure 7 below. This makes any potential variation in crop management inputs easy to implement in this site. However, the only significant difference between the two MZ was soil CEC, stem counts and the tuber sizes.

Figure 6. Potential management zones based on potato yields and tuber size distribution (McCarville site)

Grower planning – McCarville

Currently the grower cultivates the entire paddock, and then does not plant a central access way, as marked as the dotted line (Figure 6) above to provide access to other parts of the paddock. It would be easy for the grower to locate the central access way in future years on the transition from MZ 1 to MZ 2. There was a significant difference between the proportion of 45-80mm tubers, the stem numbers and the soil CEC in each MZ.

Conclusion

This work has quantified the wide range of yields, tuber size and soil characteristics present in two typical commercial potato paddocks. It has also given a practical analysis of crop agronomic decision that can be made by growers based on geospatial crop and soil data to inform crop management decisions in future.

There appeared to be no strong correlations between the soil chemical properties and the tuber sizes. One reason might be that not enough point samples were taken at a single paddock to stand out from the 'noises' of the data. Furthermore, some critical factors for tuber growth such as seeding spacing and soil moisture (Ifenkwe et al., 1974; Mackerron, et al., 1988; Love & Thompson-Johns, 1999) will need to be included in further research to determine what leads to the spatial variation of tuber sizes in potato crops.

Spatial clustering analysis had established a good basis for site-specific management by identifying MZ. FAR will use the findings of this work to identify different MZ in potato growers' paddocks, and then in conjunction with the growers investigate practical ways to improve crop performance by site-specific management techniques.

Acknowledgments

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Potatoes NZ

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